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Prishtinë, 2024

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Title of thesis:

**MECHATRONIC SYSTEMS FOR DIESEL FUEL SUPPLY
CONTROL - CR/EDC 15 SIMULATOR**

Subject:

Vehicle Mechatronics

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ABSTRACT

Automobiles produced in recent years are equipped with sophisticated systems that include sensors and intelligent actuators, which transmit data to the central Electronic Control Unit (ECU). The ECU analyses this information to adjust engine performance and optimize combustion, resulting in improved fuel efficiency and lower emissions.

The mechatronic control system of the diesel fuel supply in modern vehicles plays a crucial role in increasing the efficiency and performance of diesel engines. These systems are incorporated in advanced technologies such as Common Rail (CR) and the CR/EDC 15 Electronic Control Unit, which precisely manages the fuel injection process by adjusting the pressure and timing of injection according to the engine's operating conditions.

In the laboratory work conducted with the CR/EDC 15 simulator, this system serves as a valuable tool for examining the operation of a diesel engine. The simulator helps users understand how sensors and injectors operate under different conditions, enabling them to perform practical tests for diagnosing and fine-tuning fuel control systems.

The simulation panel used in the Vehicle Mechatronics Laboratory has been crucial in researching mechatronic control systems for diesel fuel supply. It offers an accurate and reliable platform for testing and analyzing engine behavior in various scenarios.

1. INTRODUCTION

A vehicle is a complex system in which each component plays its role to enable movement. The vehicle is made up of many systems, such as the braking system, steering system, power transmission system, stabilizing mechatronic systems, and more. Today, a vehicle can be described as a complex mechatronic system, composed of numerous sensors and actuators integrated into the previously mentioned systems. Thanks to mechatronic systems, driving a vehicle is easier and safer.

In addition to the components responsible for vehicle propulsion (the engine and power transmission system), which enable the vehicle to move, a crucial role is also played by systems that limit movement and slow the vehicle down. Without these systems, safe use of the vehicle in traffic would not be possible. Furthermore, systems that provide additional safety for passengers in the event of an accident are becoming increasingly important [1].

Diesel fuel supply systems have evolved significantly over the past few decades, improving the efficiency and performance of diesel engines. One of the most important technologies in this field is the mechatronic fuel control system through the Common Rail (CR) system and the Electronic Control Unit (EDC 15). This system is used to precisely manage the fuel injection process, depending on various operating conditions of the engine, thereby increasing fuel efficiency and reducing environmental pollution.

Through the use of the CR/EDC 15 simulator, an advanced laboratory device, students and professionals have the opportunity to study and understand in detail the operation of diesel injection systems. This simulator provides a controlled environment for analysing the interactions

between sensors, actuators, and other key components of the system. Its study and application contribute to the preparation of future specialists for the maintenance, diagnosis, and optimization of diesel engines, focusing on the challenges posed by the modern automotive industry in both technological and environmental aspects.

In the Vehicle Mechatronics Laboratory, there is a special platform produced by AutoEDU, Lithuania, which simulates the diesel fuel injection and engine control system (COMMON RAIL - CR/EDC 15) controlled by the Bosch EDC 15 C3-4 ECU. This simulator is mounted on a mobile aluminium frame, as shown in Figure 1.1.

This simulation platform allows the real-time monitoring of all operational parameters of the engine and provides a device that enables students to learn the structure of the engine control system, its operating modes, and perform various measurements, tests, and other diagnostic procedures with the advanced diesel injection system.

Figure 1.1: CR/EDC 15 Simulation Platform

The platform consists of two parts: one for demonstrating the electronic control system of the engine's operation (Figure 1.1, left side); while the other part is designed to demonstrate the operation of the high-pressure pump and injectors (Figure 1.1, right side). Both parts are interconnected and function as a single system.

The simulation platform consists of:

Electrical installation diagram

- with connectors for measuring and simulating the codes generated in an electrical system,
- System components that monitor the operation,
- Simulation of more than 20 faults through the integrated voltmeter,
- PPS1 – Gas pedal position sensor I,
- Gas pedal position sensor II,
- Air temperature sensor (ACT),
- Airflow sensor (MAF),
- High-pressure fuel sensor (FPS),
- Compressed air pressure sensor (MAP),
- Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) sensor,
- Engine temperature sensor (CTS),
- Fuel temperature sensor (FTS).

The platform is connected to the Bosch diagnostic device via OBDII, enabling fault detection in the system and the measurement of electrical signal parameters from each system component (sensors or actuators) [2].

2. DIESEL FUEL SUPPLY SYSTEM FOR INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINES

2.1. Main components of the fuel supply system

The diesel fuel supply system is a complex network of components that work together to deliver fuel to the engine for internal combustion. Understanding the various parts, as shown in Figure 2.1, is essential for maintaining its performance and ensuring smooth operation.

This chapter presents the key components of a diesel fuel supply system, including (Figure 2.1):

- The fuel tank,
- The electric fuel pump,
- The fuel filter,
- The high-pressure pump,
- The pressure regulator, and
- The Common Rail system.

Figure 2.1. Key components of the diesel fuel supply system

The fuel tank is where the fuel is stored (deposited) in a vehicle. It functions as a reservoir, holding a specific amount of fuel that will be used by the internal combustion engine. The fuel tank shown in Figure 2.2 is typically made from durable materials like steel or aluminium to resist the corrosive nature of fuels such as diesel or gasoline. Fuel tanks are designed to be securely mounted to the vehicle's chassis to prevent fuel leakage or spillage.

Figure 2.2. Fuel tank

The electric fuel pump is responsible for drawing fuel from the tank and sending it to the high-pressure pump of an internal combustion engine. In Figure 2.3, the electric fuel pump is shown, playing a crucial role in maintaining the proper fuel pressure required for efficient combustion. Fuel pumps can be mechanical or electric, depending on the vehicle model. Mechanical fuel pumps are driven by the engine's camshaft, while electric fuel pumps are powered by the vehicle's electrical system.

Figure 2.3. Electric fuel pump

The fuel filter is a crucial component that helps remove impurities and contaminants from the fuel before it reaches the high-pressure pump. In Figure 2.4, the fuel filter is shown, acting as a barrier to prevent any dirt, debris, or water from entering the fuel system and causing damage. Over time, the fuel filter can become clogged with particles, reducing the flow of fuel and affecting engine performance. Regular replacement of the fuel filter is necessary to ensure optimal filtration and prevent any issues [4].

Figure 2.4. Fuel filter

The high-pressure pump / fuel pressure regulator is a system that works by controlling the pressure applied to the fuel entering the high-pressure pump (Figure 2.5a), through the fuel injectors. If the fuel pressure regulator is absent, the fuel will enter the fuel injection systems directly. The role of a pressure regulator is to ensure a steady supply of fuel to keep the vehicle engine running smoothly. In its structure, as shown in Figure 2.5b, the fuel pressure regulator contains a diaphragm to control the position of the ball or bypass valve. The bypass valve opens

and closes to regulate the proper pressure for a consistent fuel supply, allowing fuel to flow through as needed [3].

Figure 2.5. Pressure regulators (a) and Internal part of the regulator (b) [5]

Common Rail is a special diesel fuel injection system. The main advantage of this system is its wide range of pressure and injection timing. This is achieved by creating a separate high-pressure (high-pressure pump) and the injection of fuel (injectors). The distribution of fuel in the rail (Common Rail), as shown in Figure 2.6, allows for the circulation of fuel under pressure. The Common Rail system flexibly adapts the fuel injection process for the internal combustion engine [4].

Figure 2.6. Common rail (CR) [5]

2.2. Operating principle of the fuel supply system

Fuel is introduced into the internal combustion engine when the piston is near the top of its stroke or in the pre-combustion chamber, and in other cases, it is directly injected into the combustion chamber of the piston-cylinder.

Except for small high-speed systems, diesel engines typically use direct fuel injection.

The fuel injection systems of diesel engines (Figure 2.7) are typically designed to ensure injection pressures in the range of 7 to 70 [MPa] (70 to 700 [bar]). However, there are some systems with higher pressures.

Figure 2.7. Fuel injection system [5]

Accurate control of fuel injection is critical for the performance of a diesel engine. Since the entire combustion process is controlled by fuel injection, the injection must begin at the correct position of the piston (i.e., the injection angle). Initially, the fuel burns with almost unchanged volume as the piston is near the top of its stroke. As the piston moves away from this position, the fuel injection continues, and the combustion process then appears as a nearly constant pressure process.

The combustion process in a diesel engine is heterogeneous – meaning, the fuel and air are not mixed before the combustion begins. Consequently, the rapid evaporation and mixing of the fuel with air is very important for the complete combustion of the injected fuel. The structure of the injector nozzle is crucial, especially in direct injection engines.

The engine power is generated during the combustion process. The combustion process (Figure 2.8) involves the combustion of fuel at steady pressure and the expansion of hot gases after the injection is stopped.

Figure 2.8. Fuel injection procedure [5]

Diesel engines are often equipped with a turbocharger and subsequently cooled. Adding a turbocharger and the subsequent intercooler can improve the performance of a diesel engine in terms of both power and efficiency.

The most important feature of a diesel engine is its efficiency. By compressing air instead of using a fuel-air mixture, the diesel engine is not limited by the pre-ignition problems that affect high-compression spark-ignition engines. As a result, higher compression ratios can be achieved in diesel engines compared to spark-ignition engines. Proportionally, higher theoretical cycle efficiencies are often realized when compared to the latter. It should be emphasized that for a given compression ratio, the theoretical efficiency of a spark-ignition engine is higher than that of a compression-ignition engine. However, in practice, it is possible to operate compression-ignition engines with sufficiently high compression ratios to produce higher efficiency than can be achieved with spark-ignition systems.

Diesel engines do not control power by limiting the amount of air intake. This makes them more efficient and results in lower power losses compared to spark-ignition engines. The main drawback of diesel engines is their emission of air pollutants. These engines typically emit high levels of particulate matter (soot), reactive nitrogen compounds (commonly referred to as NO_x), and odor, compared to spark-ignition engines. Consequently, Figure 2.9 shows the flow of exhaust gases in the small engine category.

Figure 2.9. Air pollution from HC, CO₂, N₂, O₂ [5]

A diesel engine is started by driving it with an external energy source until the conditions are created for the engine to run on its own power. The simplest starting method involves admitting air from a high-pressure source — around 1.7 to nearly 2.4 [MPa] — into each of the cylinders in the firing order. The compressed air heats up enough to ignite the fuel. Other starting methods include auxiliary devices, such as admitting bursts of compressed air into an air-started engine, which is used to rotate the flywheel of a large engine; supplying electric current to a starter motor, which is similarly connected to the engine's flywheel; or using a small gasoline engine mounted on the engine's flywheel. The choice of the most suitable starting method depends on the engine's physical size, the nature of the connected load, and whether the load can be released during the start up.

2.3. Types of Fuel Systems

Fuel injection systems come in different types, each with its own specific qualities and benefits. Below are listed some of the most typical models of fuel injection systems:

- Rotary Distributor Pump Injection
- Direct Injection (DI)
- Indirect Injection (IDI)
- Common Rail Injection
- Sequential Fuel Injection

- Individual Injection System

2.3.1. Rotary distributor pump injection

Rotary fuel systems use a distributor or a rotary vane pump. This type has a shaft with a single piston. Although there are four injectors, the number of plungers remains one, as shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10. Rotary distributor pump

The piston is located on the shaft of the pump, which rotates. Each rotation angle corresponds to a specific amount of fuel, and as the piston passes through the fuel volume, the fuel is injected into an injector. Therefore, if there are four injectors, there are four fuel quantities that surround the pump shaft.

Advantages

- It doesn't take up much space, making it suitable for vehicles with limited space.
- Few moving parts, allowing the energy produced to be more efficient.

Disadvantages

- The fuel pressure is relatively low, which makes it less suitable for high-capacity diesel engines that require higher fuel pressures to operate efficiently.

2.3.2. Direct injection (DI)

Instead of the intake manifold or throttle body, Direct Injection (DI) (Figure 2.11) injects the fuel directly into the engine's combustion chamber. This system allows for more precise control over

the fuel-air mixture, which can improve engine performance, increase fuel efficiency, and reduce emissions [7].

Figure 2.11: Direct injection (DI)

These are usually managed by an Electronic Control Unit (ECU), which determines the optimal fuel delivery using data from various sensors. Direct fuel delivery into the combustion chamber allows for the optimization of the fuel-air mixture for different engine conditions, such as high-load operation or low-speed driving [7].

2.3.3. Indirect injection (IDI)

Indirect Injection (IDI) is a method of ignition by fuel spray, which occurs in a separate chamber known as the pre-combustion chamber.

Figure 2.12. Indirect fuel injection

The main difference lies in the injection method. In the DI system, the fuel is directly sprayed into the combustion chamber. However, in the IDI system (Figure 2.12), the fuel is sprayed into the pre-combustion chamber. Once ignited, the expansion process sends the combustion gasses into the main combustion chamber to burn the remaining air in it.

However, today the IDI system is no longer widely used by most manufacturers, as the process is longer, and this system has many disadvantages compared to the DI system. As a result, modern vehicles rarely use the IDI system for commercial vehicles, whether light or heavy-duty [7].

2.3.4. Common Rail injection

Common Rail is an electronically controlled diesel fuel system. This means that in the common rail system, there will be a series of sensors monitored by the ECU (Electronic Control Unit), as shown in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13. Common Rail injection

The first difference lies in the fuel pump. The common rail system has two pumps, as shown in Figure 2.13. The first pump is for transferring fuel from the fuel tank to the fuel line, and the second is a high-pressure pump used to increase the fuel pressure.

For a high-pressure pump, it is also different from the two types mentioned earlier. The pump used in the Common Rail system is continuous, meaning that the pump will continue to pressurize the fuel at a constant pressure.

Meanwhile, to control the fuel injection, each injector will regulate it based on a command from the ECU. In this system, the injector functions like a water faucet that can be adjusted to open and close for a specified duration.

2.3.5. Sequential fuel injection

In a continuous fuel injection system, the fuel is distributed in a specific order to the engine cylinders based on the engine's firing order. Figure 2.13 shows the case when the engine is at idle, where the fuel may remain for up to 150 milliseconds, because all injectors spray at the same time or sequentially [7].

Figure 2.14: Sequential fuel injection

Sequential fuel injection has the advantage of allowing the engine to respond more quickly to sudden driver changes, as shown in Figure 2.14. This is because the valve does not need to wait for the engine to complete a full rotation; instead, it only needs to wait for the next intake valve to open [7].

2.3.6. Individual fuel injection system

Different fuel supply systems have a separate pump for each cylinder. This means that the number of pumps corresponds to the number of injectors. This happens because each piston serves one injector, so if there are four injectors, there will be four systems arranged in a row.

There is a camshaft with lobes, where each lobe presses a piston at the right time. When the piston is pressed against the lobe, the fuel will be injected. It can be said that the number of lobes is equal to the number of injectors, and the angle of the lobe is also adjusted according to the ignition timing.

Figure 2.15. Individual injection system

The main advantages are the injection pressure, which can reach up to 1240 [bar]. With this pressure, this pump is suitable for use in standard large-capacity diesel engines.

The injection system of the unit and the intake pump are similar to the concept of the individual injection system (Figure 2.15), because each cylinder has an independent injection system.

Unit injection system: Each cylinder has independent injection units (pump and injector together). This system provides each cylinder with an individual system that supplies fuel, which is the basic concept of the individual fuel system.

Intake pump: It is a variant of the individual injection system, where each cylinder has its own pump integrated with the injector. This makes the intake pump a form of the individual injection system, as each cylinder receives its controlled amount of fuel.

2.4. Diagnosis and maintenance of the fuel supply system

There are many reasons for a defect in the fuel supply system, which will cause significant changes in the shape and amplitude of the waveform in the high-pressure fuel pipeline. According to the eight parameters of the waveform state of the high-pressure fuel pipeline, namely maximum pressure, drop pressure, injection pressure, sub-maximum pressure, waveform amplitude, rising edge width, waveform width, and maximum exhaust width, defect conditions, including needle valve stick, needle valve leakage, distribution valve failure, and insufficient oil supply, can be identified and diagnosed, and the normal condition is recognized and diagnosed [7].

2.4.1. Diagnosis and simulation of defects

A decrease in engine power can be caused by air entering the fuel supply system, contamination of the air filter, insufficient fuel supply, improper adjustment of the injection timing, deterioration of fuel injection from the injector, and uneven or insufficient fuel supply from the high-pressure fuel pump due to low compression and improper use of the specified fuel.

Maintenance of the diesel engine fuel supply system:

In the maintenance of the fuel supply system, diagnosis, adjustment, determination of system density, condition of fuel and air filters, and the functioning of the fuel transfer pump and high-pressure fuel pump are checked and adjusted [8].

The tightness of the system is of particular importance. If it fails, air will be drawn into the system from the tank to the fuel pump, leading to increased fuel consumption and malfunctioning of the equipment. This part is checked with the help of a special tool box, while the remaining parts are visually inspected, and the fuel and air filters are checked through inspection.

2.4.2. The fuel supply system and the fuel pressure waveform

The diesel fuel is injected into the cylinders at the correct time, in the appropriate quantity, and at the required pressure, ensuring that it mixes and combusts rapidly with the air. The fuel supply system is made up of several critical components, including the fuel tank, fuel filter, low-pressure fuel lines, fuel pump, injection pump, high-pressure fuel lines, injectors, and other related parts (Figure 2.16). The complex structure of the system increases the potential for failure, highlighting the need for thorough monitoring and maintenance.

Figure 2.16. Composition of the fuel supply system

The characteristics of the pressure waveform of the high-pressure fuel can be analysed to determine the cause of defects.

Figure 2.17. Normal pressure waveform

The cause of failure can be determined by analysing the characteristics of the pressure waveform of the fuel in the high-pressure oil circuit. Figure 2.17 shows the normal pressure waveform and its characteristic parameters [8].

3. SENSORS AND ACTUATORS USED IN THE COMMON RAIL SYSTEM

3.1. Introduction to the Common Rail system

"Common Rail" (CR) is a diesel fuel injection system. The main advantage of this system is that it offers a wide range of injection pressures and injection timings. This is achieved by creating a constant pressure (high-pressure pump) and injecting fuel through injectors. The Common Rail system flexibly adapts the fuel injection process to the engine. This is achieved through:

- High pressure (up to 2400 bar) fuel injection;
- Pressure (200 – 2400 bar) regulated in working mode;
- Adjustable starting point for fuel supply;
- Ability to perform multiple pilot and post injections.
- The Common Rail system consists of the following main components:
 - Low-pressure fuel supply section (fuel tank, pipes, filters, low-pressure fuel pump);
 - High-pressure fuel supply section (high-pressure fuel pump, pipes, injectors);
 - Electronic control system (EDC) with sensors, control unit, and actuators.

The high-speed valve (electromagnetic or piezoelectric) installed in the injectors of the Common Rail system, which opens and closes the injector. In this way, the injection process can be operated independently for each cylinder. The CR system can set the pressure of the system in

the operating mode. The pressure is set by the pressure control valve or the pressure regulating valve [9].

3.2. Operating principle

In the CR fuel injection system, the creation of fuel pressure is separate from the injection, as shown in Figure 3.1. Regardless of the engine speed and the amount of fuel injected, the fuel injection pressure is created here. The electronic control system (EDC) operates on individual components, controlling the injector opening and duration.

Figure 3.1. CR fuel injection system

The creation of fuel pressure and injection are separated by the pipelines. The fuel, which is ready for injection, is compressed and then stored in the Common Rail. The high-pressure pump continuously supplies fuel and creates the desired injection pressure. Due to the continuous fuel supply, the high-pressure pump can be much smaller. The torque fluctuations required for the pump are lower than those in traditional injection systems, which significantly reduces the load on the fuel delivery pump.

High-pressure pumps are radial-arm pumps. Sectional pumps can be used for trucks. Various methods are employed to regulate the fuel pressure. In the vehicle's Common Rail system, the desired pressure is regulated by the pressure control valve located on the high-pressure side. Fuel that is not required for injection is returned to the low-pressure circuit through the pressure control valve. With this regulation, the pressure in the Common Rail can be adjusted very quickly as the operating mode changes.

Figure 3.2. Fuel distribution control [5]

A pressure regulation of this type was used in the early Common Rail systems. The pressure control valve is sometimes attached to the Common Rail, or alternatively, to the high-pressure pump. Another method of pressure control is possible on the suction side. The pressure metering valve in the high-pressure pump ensures that the pump delivers exactly the required amount of fuel to the Common Rail to maintain the desired system pressure. In case of a malfunction, the pressure relief valve prevents the rail pressure from exceeding the maximum limit.

Fuel distribution control, as shown in Figure 3.3, on the suction side reduces the amount of fuel under high pressure and decreases the input power to the pump. This, in turn, reduces the overall fuel consumption. The temperature of the fuel flowing into the fuel tank is reduced, unlike the method of control on the high-pressure side. By using a dual actuator system, one on the suction side and the other on the high-pressure side, the advantages of both control approaches are integrated. Fuel injection is directed straight into the engine's combustion chambers. The fuel for

the injectors is supplied by the Common Rail via a short high-pressure pipe. The Engine Control Unit (ECU) operates the valve integrated into the injector, which opens and closes the nozzle. The amount of fuel injected depends on the duration the injector is open and the system pressure. When the pressure is constant, it is proportional to the duration of the control valve's open position and is independent of engine speed.

The application of pilot or multiple injections in the Common Rail system helps reduce harmful emissions and lowers engine noise during operation. By repeatedly actuating a very fast control valve, multiple injections (up to five per working cycle) can be performed. The injector needle is hydraulically closed, which ensures a smooth and controlled end to each injection [9].

3.3. Control system

The engine control unit (ECU) measures the position of the throttle pedal and the parameters of the engine and vehicle operating mode directly with the help of sensors. These modes include:

- Speed of the camshaft and the rotation angle;
- Pressure in the fuel rail;
- Pressure of the supplied intake air;
- Intake air, coolant, and fuel temperature;
- Mass of intake air;
- Steering speed;
- Other settings (e.g., brake pedal pressure, clutch, etc.).

The control unit evaluates the input signals and calculates the control valve or metering valve signals, injectors, exhaust gas recirculation valve, and synchronized turbocharger control valve for the combustion process. The necessary conditions for activating the small injector can be achieved with the help of optimized high-pressure control valves and special control mechanisms. The system – timing control – uses the signals from the camshaft and crankshaft sensors and adjusts the injection timing according to the engine's status. The electronic control system ensures the precise dosing of the injected fuel quantity. Furthermore, the EDC allows the use of additional functions that enhance performance and driving comfort.

Figure 3.3. The map of the start of fuel injection

The basic functions regulate the required injection of diesel fuel at the right moment and at a precise pressure. This ensures smooth engine operation and efficiency. To compensate for injection within the system and engine limits, correction functions are applied. The correction functions include: injector delivery compensation, zero delivery calibration, fuel balance control, and adjustment of the average fuel quantity.

Additional control and regulation functions reduce the emission of harmful substances and fuel consumption. The additional functions are: exhaust gas recirculation control, boost pressure control, cruise control, and electronic protection [9].

3.4. The role of sensors and actuators in the Common Rail system

New development trends in the automotive industry require advanced and sophisticated technologies with high reliability, low production costs, high precision, and minimal information delay. Many of the demands placed on vehicles are closely tied to the dynamic development of electronics and advanced technologies.

There are new devices not only for controlling and regulating the functions of specific systems, but these devices are also available for managing the operation of the engine and chassis, as well as ensuring safety and passenger comfort.

Regarding these new electronic elements, referred to as sensors, they are used to measure scalar and vector physical quantities. The fundamental requirement is that the signals from these

transmitters and sensors are evaluated and processed within a very short time. This allows the vehicle to respond to external influences in real time or to mitigate dangerous situations.

Sensors provide information about various quantities (Figure 3.4), which are then transmitted via electrical signals to the electronic control unit (ECU - Processor). The processor then acts on the actuator – the executing mechanism.

Figure 3.4: The connection between the brain hemispheres and the hands

In Figure 3.5, the schematic representation of the interconnection between the sensors (transmitters) of different constructive forms and types with the actuators (executing organs) through the electronic control unit (ECU) is shown.

Figure 3.5. The schematic of the interconnection between the sensors and actuators through the electronic control unit [1]

3.4.1. The sensors found in the Common Rail

Sensors play a crucial role in this system by providing real-time data on various parameters. These sensors are integrated into the engine control unit (ECU), enabling precise control of fuel injection, which helps reduce emissions and increase fuel efficiency. Through sensor technology, the

Common Rail system effectively monitors the combustion processes, ensuring optimal performance under all operating conditions. Some of these sensors include:

The Common Rail fuel pressure sensor is used to measure the fuel pressure in the fuel rail. The sensor is designed in such a way that, due to pressure changes, a metal diaphragm alters its geometric shape, which is then recorded by the sensor mounted on it, as shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6. The Common Rail sensor

The signal from the sensor is processed by an evaluation circuit, and it transmits information to the engine control unit.

The fuel temperature sensor measures the temperature of the fuel (Figure 3.7) and sends information to the engine control unit. The possible measurement range is from -50 to 190 °C.

Figure 3.7. The fuel temperature sensor

The air intake flow sensor is located between the air filter and the intake manifold. There are no mechanically moving parts in the sensor. The mass air intake sensor consists of a tube that directs the airflow, a hot wire placed in the tube, and a temperature sensor. When the air passes through the tube, the temperature of the hot wire decreases, as shown in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8. The air intake flow sensor (a) and the temperature sensor (b)

The engine control unit reacts to changes in temperature (while air flows, the wire cools) and accordingly increases or decreases the current necessary to maintain the temperature of the hot wire. The integrated electronic flow controller changes the wire's current properties so that the temperature of the hot wire remains around 120 °C at all times.

With the increase in airflow and mass, the hot wire cools. To maintain a constant wire temperature, the current power must be increased. If the airflow decreases, meaning the mass of air flowing is reduced, less current is needed to maintain the wire's temperature. These changes in power flow are recorded and transmitted to the engine control module. The control unit processes the information received from the mass air flow sensor and other sensors, and accordingly adjusts the amount of fuel. After the engine stops, the hot wire function is activated, aiming to burn off any accumulated dirt on the wire [9].

The gas pedal sensor consists of two potentiometers mounted on the same shaft. The engine control unit, by evaluating the voltage on both potentiometers, can determine the position of the pedal. Due to the change in the pedal position, the resistance value also changes. The variable voltage is also evaluated by the engine control unit. The engine control unit determines the position of the gas pedal from these two voltages. By comparing these two voltage values, the engine control unit can check if the gas pedal position sensors are functioning correctly. Each gas pedal

sensor has cables for electrical power connection, ground (earth), and signal, as shown in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9. The gas pedal sensor

In one of these two sensors, an additional resistance is added to distinguish the signals. In the case of failure, the voltage values of a sensor change, and with this, the engine control unit detects the defect. After pressing the brake pedal, as shown in Figure 3.9, the motor shaft speed decreases to a minimum. Under unfavourable conditions and in the case of failure of both potentiometers, the engine control unit will not be able to detect this. In this case, the engine speed increases and does not respond to the pressing of the pedal [9].

The shaft rotation sensors with bumps are used to measure the frequency of the shaft's rotation (Figure 3.10) and to record the shaft's position (the piston position).

Figure 3.10. The sensor for measuring the number of rotations of the shaft with bumps

The sensor is placed in front of the ferromagnetic pulse wheel. They are separated by an air gap. There is a ferromagnetic core in the sensor, which is surrounded by a coil. The pole bar is connected to a permanent magnet. The magnetic field is spread within the pole bar into the pulse wheel. The size of the magnetic field passing through the coil depends on what is in front of the sensor. It could be a gap in the pulse wheel or a tooth [9].

The coolant temperature sensor is mounted so that the tip of the heat-sensitive sensor makes direct contact with the coolant, as shown in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11. The coolant temperature sensor

The sensor's resistance changes depending on the coolant temperature. The resistance of the temperature coefficient sensor decreases as the coolant temperature increases. As the resistance decreases, the voltage signal that reaches the engine control unit increases. The magnitude of the signal is proportional to the coolant temperature. The engine control unit compares the stored voltage-to-temperature dependency from the memory and calculates the current coolant temperature based on the voltage value. The signal received from the coolant temperature sensor is used for fuel correction, adjusting the injection start point, exhaust gas recirculation control, glow plug control, and further adjustment of engine heating. In the event of a failure of the coolant temperature sensor, the engine control unit operates the engine as if it were cold. The operating range of the coolant temperature sensor is 10-120 °C [9].

4. MECHATRONIC DIESEL FUEL SUPPLY CONTROL SYSTEM - CREDC 15 SIMULATOR

4.1. CR/EDC

The training simulator has been created for the demonstration and study of the fuel supply in the Common Rail injection system of internal combustion engines and the operation of the EDC 15 engine control. With the help of this panel, shown in Figure 4.1, the operating parameters of the engine can be adjusted and the fuel injection can be monitored. It is possible to simulate changes in parameters such as air mass, air pressure, coolant temperature, bump shaft speed, and the throttle pedal position.

Figure 4.1. CR/EDC 15 Simulator Platform

By changing the parameters, the signals entering the engine control unit (ECU) also change. The evaluation of the changes in the input signals is done by the ECU, which then sends the necessary commands to the actuators: the fuel quantity is increased, the cooling fan is turned on, etc.

The simulation platform consists of two parts. In the first part of the platform, most of the sensors and actuators, the engine control unit, the diagnostic connector, the electrical diagram, and the throttle pedal are mounted. In the second part of the platform, the power supply to the panel, the electric motor, the fuel pump, injectors, measuring cylinders, and some sensors are mounted. Both parts are movable as they are placed on wheels and are connected by cables. This cable has a connector, which is connected to the bottom part of the first panel. The second part of the cable is connected to the second part of the platform and cannot be disconnected.

The cable connector linking both parts of the platform can only be connected in one position. It is impossible to connect the parts incorrectly due to the special design of the connector. Once connected, it is locked by bending the left and right fasteners. Before disconnecting the connector, it is necessary to unlock the fasteners.

The main power cable is connected to the ~220V network only after both parts of the platform are electrically connected. Disconnection is performed in the reverse order: the cable is withdrawn from the ~220V network, and the cable that connects the two parts of the platform is disconnected. The main power cable is installed in the second part of the platform.

The simulation platform is based on the Renault Laguna II vehicle. Using computer diagnostics and vehicle identification, the following information is displayed: Brand: Renault, Model: Laguna II, Production year: 03/2001 – 12/2005, Engine capacity: 1.9L DCI, Engine power: 88 kW, Engine code: F9Q 750. The engine code can be found in the electrical diagram of the platform. The engine idle speed is 750 – 850 rpm.

4.2. Components of the CREDC 15 Panel.

4.2.1. The first part of the panel.

In the first part of the panel, as shown in Figure 4.2, most of the sensors and actuators, the engine control unit, the diagnostic connector, the electrical diagram, and the throttle pedal are mounted. In general, this part of the panel provides a detailed and integrated view of the key components necessary for the operation and management of the vehicle's engine.

Figure 4.2. The first part of the panel

(1) Main engine control relay:

The relay activates and deactivates the power supply to the engine control system, ensuring the proper operation of the electronic components, Figure 4.3.

(2) Coolant blower motor relay I:

The relay controls the operation of the coolant blower motor, helping to maintain the optimal engine temperature, Figure 4.3.

(3) Coolant blower motor relay II:

The relay provides enhanced control for the operation of the coolant blower motor, helping to regulate the engine temperature, Figure 4.3.

(4) Engine coolant heater three relays:

The three relays activate and deactivate the engine coolant heater, helping to maintain the proper temperature for ignition and optimal engine operation in cold conditions, Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3. Motor relays

(5) Electrical diagram with fault simulation connections:

This diagram shows the electrical connections and defect simulation points for training and diagnostic purposes, Figure 4.4. All the main components are visible here: sensors, actuators, data transmission lines, and the diagnostic connector. Below this schematic, it is possible to see the circuits of the components, the pin numbers of the connections, the component numbers, and the legend for the coding of these numbers.

There are 24 connections, twelve in each row. After disconnecting any connection, the signal values are distorted or damaged. The engine control unit recognizes this as a defect.

The connections have two contacts that link the circuit. The third contact is intended for connecting measurement instruments. The open contacts installed in the electrical diagram are for connecting measurement instruments and monitoring signals. For example, contact 30 (red) is a constant battery plus. Contact 31- is the ground, a constant battery minus

Figure 4.4. Electrical diagram

(6) Voltmeter TFT:

This voltmeter measures the voltage in the motor's electrical system and displays it on a TFT (Thin Film Transistor) screen for easy monitoring, Figure 4.5.

(7) Tachometer:

This instrument measures and displays the engine's revolutions per minute (RPM), Figure 4.5.

(8) Simulator for choosing different parameters for monitoring on the screen:

This simulator allows the selection and monitoring of various engine parameters on the screen for analysis and diagnostics, Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5. The voltmeter, tachometer, and the simulator for parameter selection

(9) Glow plug control unit: This unit manages the activation of the heaters to ensure proper engine ignition, especially in cold conditions, Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6. Engine heater control unit

(10) Mass-Air flow sensor simulator, intake air temperature sensor and fan:

This simulator imitates the operation of the mass air flow sensor and the intake air temperature sensor, as well as controls the operation of the fan, Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7. Intake air pressure sensor (a), Air temperature sensor (b)

(11) Intake air control valve:

This valve controls the amount of air entering the engine to ensure an optimal air-fuel mixture, Figure 4.8

Figure 4.8. Intake air control valve

(12) Diagram of the Common rail fuel injection system:

This diagram shows the components and connections of the Common Rail fuel injection system, Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9. Diagram of the Common Rail fuel injection system

(13) Mass-Air flow sensor simulator:

This simulator imitates the operation of the air intake sensor to test and diagnose the air intake system, Figure 4.11.

(14) Turbocharger boost pressure sender:

This sensor monitors the boost pressure created by the turbocharger to ensure the optimal operation of the engine, Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10. Turbocharger boost pressure sensor

(15) Turbocharger boost pressure sensor simulator:

This simulator imitates the operation of the turbocharger boost pressure sensor for diagnostic purposes, Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11. Air intake sensor simulator (a) and turbocharger boost pressure sensor simulator (b)

(16) CR/EDC 15 Electronic control unit:

This unit controls the operation of the Common Rail fuel injection system and manages the engine parameters for optimal performance, Figure 4.12.

Figure 4.12. ECU - Electronic Control Unit

(17) Turbocharger wastegate control valve:

This valve controls the amount of exhaust gases passing through the turbocharger to manage the boost pressure, Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13. Turbocharger emission control valve

(18) Engine coolant temperature sensor simulator:

This simulator imitates the operation of the engine coolant temperature sensor for diagnostic and training purposes, Figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14. Engine coolant temperature sensor simulator

(19) Clutch pedal position switch:

This switch monitors the position of the clutch pedal to assist in managing engine functions during gear shifting, Figure 4.15.

(20) Brake pedal position switch:

This switch monitors the application of the brake pedal and can affect engine control and safety systems, Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.15. Pedal position and brake switch

(21) Exhaust gas recirculation valve and exhaust gas recirculation potentiometer:

They control and monitor the amount of exhaust gases recirculated into the engine to reduce emissions, Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16. Exhaust gas recirculation valve

(22) Accelerator pedal position sensor:

This sensor detects the position of the accelerator pedal and transmits the information to the ECU to manage the engine power and speed, Figure 4.17.

Figure 4.17. Gas pedal and gas pedal position sensor

(23) LED indicators:

Yellow – the panel is on, red – the ignition is activated, green – the panel is operational (the fuel pump is operating). These LED indicators display the operational status of the training panel, Figure 4.18.

Figure 4.18. LED Indicators

(24) Engine coolant temperature sensor: This sensor monitors the engine coolant temperature to prevent overheating and optimize performance, Figure 4.19.

Figure 4.19. Engine coolant temperature sensor

(25) Ignition switch with a key:

This switch is used to turn the engine on and off, activating the necessary systems for operation, Figure 4.20.

(26) Manual adjuster of the engine crankshaft speed:

This adjuster allows for the manual adjustment of the engine crankshaft speed for training and testing purposes, Figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20. Manual speed regulator of the crankshaft with engine lobes

(27) Glow plugs (R5-I...IV):

These heaters are used to warm the combustion chambers of a diesel engine, facilitating engine starting in cold conditions, Figure 4.21.

Figure 4.21. Engine heaters

(28) Battery terminals:

These terminals connect the battery to the engine's electrical system to supply power to the electronic components, Figure 4.22.

(29) Diagnostic connector:

This connector is used to connect diagnostic equipment to the engine's electronic system for control and diagnostic purposes, Figure 4.22.

(30) 10A and 30A Fuses (F6 and F3):

These fuses protect the engine's electrical system from overloads and short circuits, ensuring its safe operation, Figure 4.22 [9].

Figure 4.22. Battery terminals, diagnostic connector, ignition key, as well as fuses

4.2.2. The second part of the panel

In the second part of the panel, shown in Figure 4.23, the power supply of the panel, the electric motor, the fuel pump, the injectors, the measuring cylinders, and some sensors are mounted.

In general, this part of the panel provides a detailed view of the key components that help simulate and test the operation of the engine and its related systems [9].

Figure 4.23. The second part of the panel

(1) Fuel pressure relief valve: This valve controls and relieves excess pressure in the fuel supply system to prevent damage and ensure the stable operation of the engine, Figure 4.24.

Figure 4.24. Fuel pressure relief valve

(2) **Fuel rail:** This is a pipe or line that distributes fuel under pressure from the fuel pump to the fuel injectors, Figure 4.25.

Figure 4.25. The pipe that distributes fuel flow

(3) **Fuel injector (Y3-I... IV):** These injectors inject fuel into the engine cylinders in the correct quantity and pressure to ensure optimal combustion, Figure 4.26.

Figure 4.26. Fuel injector (Y3-I... IV)

(4) **Fuel rail pressure sensor:** This sensor monitors the fuel pressure in the fuel flow and transmits the data to the engine's electronic control unit (ECU), Figure 4.27.

Figure 4.27. Fuel rail pressure sensor

(5) Drain pipes for the overflow measurement cylinders:

These pipes direct excess fuel from the flow measurement cylinder to the overflow, Figure 4.28.

Figure 4.28. Pipe

(6) Measurement cylinder for fuel back leak:

This cylinder measures the amount of fuel returned from the injectors after combustion, Figure 4.29.

Figure 4.29. Measurement cylinder for fuel back leak

(7) Measurement cylinder for injected fuel:

This cylinder measures the amount of fuel that has been injected into the engine cylinders, Figure 4.30.

Figure 4.30. Measurement cylinder for injected fuel

(8) Tap for fuel back leak:

This valve allows or stops the flow of return fuel in the system, Figure 4.31.

Figure 4.31. Tap for fuel back leak

(9) Tap for injected fuel:

This valve allows or stops the flow of fuel injected into the system, Figure 4.32.

Figure 4.32. Tap for injected fuel

(10) Fuel temperature sensor:

This sensor measures the fuel temperature and transmits the data to the engine's electronic control unit (ECU), Figure 4.33.

Figure 4.33. Fuel temperature sensor

(11) Fuel cooler

This component cools the fuel to maintain the proper operating temperature and improve the efficiency of the fuel supply system, Figure 4.34.

Figure 4.34. Fuel cooler

(12) Manual rubber fuel pump:

This pump is used to manually create pressure in the fuel system for testing or to assist in fuel supply in case of pressure loss, Figure 4.35.

Figure 4.35. Manual rubber pump

(13) Fuel metering valve:

This valve, located on the fuel pump, controls the amount of fuel entering the fuel pump to ensure the correct amount of fuel in the injection system, Figure 4.36.

Figure 4.36. Fuel metering valve

(14) Camshaft position sensor:

This sensor, located on the fuel pump disks, monitors the position of the camshaft and sends the information to the engine's electronic control unit (ECU) to synchronize the fuel injection process, Figure 4.37.

Figure 4.37. Camshaft position sensor

(15) Electric box:

This box contains the electronic components and the necessary connections for the operation of the engine's electronic control system, Figure 4.38.

Figure 4.38. Electric box

(16) Electric motor:

The motor is used to drive the various components of the training and simulation system, Figure 4.39.

Figure 4.39. Electric motor

(17) Engine speed sensor:

This sensor measures the rotational speed of the engine and transmits the data to the engine's electronic control unit (ECU), Figure 4.40.

Figure 4.40. Engine speed sensor

(18) Emergency stop button:

This button is used to immediately stop the operation of the system in emergency situations to prevent damage and accidents, Figure 4.41.

(19) Main switch ON/OFF:

This switch controls the power on and off of the training system, ensuring that it is active only when necessary, Figure 4.41 [9].

Figure 4.41. Emergency stop button and main ON/OFF switch

5. PROBLEMS OF THE DIESEL SYSTEM AND SYSTEM TESTING

5.1. The most common problems in the diesel system

Diesel systems are known for their high efficiency and reliable energy delivery, but they require regular maintenance to function properly. Problems with fuel injectors, pumps, or other components of the fuel system can lead to reduced performance, resulting in increased fuel consumption and decreased engine power. To avoid these issues, the system should be cleaned and inspected routinely.

5.1.1. Injector leakage

During my internship at Baki Automobile, I observed that fuel leakage from injectors was among the most common issues. This problem typically arises from worn sealing rings or damaged parts of the injector. Such leaks result in a drop-in supply pressure, which negatively affects combustion efficiency and increases fuel consumption. If left unaddressed, this can lead to fuel loss, engine damage, and costly repairs [10].

Figure 5.1. The injector test results show significant leakage from defective injectors

5.1.2. Fuel injector leakage and oil dilution

When injectors leak, fuel pressure decreases, allowing fuel to enter the cylinder through the intake valves. The fuel can mix with the engine oil, leading to oil dilution, which may damage engine bearings and cylinder walls. In severe cases, a hydraulic lock can occur, where the engine becomes immobilized due to fluid accumulation in the pistons. This situation can bend connecting rods and cause further engine damage [11].

Figure 5.2. The reduction in oil viscosity caused by injector leakage can result in engine damage

Figure 5.3. Injector testing on the CR/EDC panel, identifying injectors with excessive fuel leakage (a), and another example (b)

5.2. Defective injector

Damage to an injector can lead to several symptoms, including:

- Black smoke from the exhaust pipes
- Uneven cylinder operation, accompanied by noticeable vibrations in the engine.
- Reduced engine power and poor vehicle performance

A damaged injector, whether due to blockage or inadequate fuel atomization, can result in irregular engine performance. Injectors that fail to distribute fuel into fine droplets should be repaired or replaced to restore normal engine operation [11].

Figure 5.4. A broken injector that requires replacement due to blockage and insufficient atomization of the fuel

5.2.1 Causes and repair of defective injectors

Injector repair involves cleaning and calibrating them. If the damage is significant, such as a blocked nozzle or mechanical issues with the injector valve, replacement is necessary, Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4. Injector replacement

The injection pressure should be 22-0.5 MPa to ensure proper fuel distribution and prevent leaks. Poor fuel quality and the lack of changes in the filter are the main reasons that damage the injectors. [11].

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the reviewed literature and the tests and analyses conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The mechatronic system of diesel fuel supply control, as shown by the CR/EDC 15 simulator, is essential for improving the performance and efficiency of diesel engines. Using Common Rail technology, this system ensures the accurate distribution of fuel through injectors controlled by the Electronic Control Unit (EDC 15). Integrated sensors and actuators collect and process data on pressure and temperature, allowing for optimal management of the injection process and the overall engine performance.
- The CR/EDC 15 simulator serves as an invaluable resource for training and laboratory studies, providing a controlled environment to explore the system's behavior under different conditions. This device allows students to engage in practical analysis of diesel engine operation and test diagnostics and maintenance in real-world scenarios.

In conclusion, this system offers significant advantages in reducing fuel consumption and lowering pollutant emissions, meeting environmental standards while enhancing performance. Furthermore, it prepares professionals to tackle the technical challenges of the future in the automotive industry, presenting innovative solutions for diesel engines.

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ETHICAL STATEMENT

I, **Elsa Lokaj**, with registration number (ID) **210805100036**

I declare that,

The thesis titled:

**MECHATRONIC SYSTEM FOR CONTROL OF DIESEL FUEL SUPPLY -
SIMULATOR CR/EDC 15**

- This presents the results of my scientific research work.
- The thesis, in whole or in part, has not been presented in any academic program at other faculties or universities.
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Prishtinë, October 2024

Elsa LOKAJ